

Evaluation of Oil Pollution and Origin in Surface Coastal Sediments of Kharg Island in the Persian Gulf

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ABSTRACT

Mirvakili, H.S., Zaker, N.H., Imani, F., 2013. Evaluation of Oil Pollution and Origin in Surface Coastal Sediments of Kharg Island in the Persian Gulf, *Proceedings 12th International Coastal Symposium* (Plymouth, England), *Journal of Coastal Research*, Special Issue No. 65, pp. 93-98, ISSN 0749-0208.

Kharg Island in the Persian Gulf is the major oil export terminal of Iran. More than 90% of the Iranian crude oil is exported through the sea oil terminals in this Island. The marine environment of the Kharg Island has been exposed to oil pollution, for several decades, from extensive oil extraction, transportation and refinement. The accidents of oil tankers and the discharges of oily wastewater from crude oil tanks, oil refineries and petrochemical industries are the major sources of the discharge of oil into the coastal area of the Island. The gas flaring emission is another source of marine oil pollution in the Island. The studies on the marine oil pollution in the Kharg Island are very limited.

In this paper the oil pollution of the shallow coastal waters adjacent to the coastline of the Kharg Island is discussed using the analysis of the concentration of hydrocarbons in the sediment samples. Eleven sediment samples were collected around the Island in 2012. The results showed a wide range of TPH concentrations with up to 5624 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in highly polluted samples from the coastal areas near the oil terminals to only a few $\mu\text{g/g}$ in non-polluted areas in the northern part of the Island. PAHs concentrations in the samples were low and ranged between 9.7 and 46.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$ indicating that the coastline sediments were not contaminated with these compounds. The use of several indexes indicated that the hydrocarbons in the polluted sediments were mainly from crude oil.

ADDITIONAL INDEX WORDS: Persian Gulf, Kharg Island, Oil contamination, Surface sediment, TPH, PAH.

INTRODUCTION

Persian Gulf is a sea at the margin of Indian ocean which makes way to Oman Sea and Indian Ocean through the Strait of Hormuz with the minimum width of 56 km. Specific condition of the Persian Gulf such as high evaporation, high salinity, aqueous species diversity, fisheries value and especially oil sources of the area which have extra importance in the world, have made the Persian Gulf a sensitive and strategic area.

Marine environment of the Persian Gulf suffers severely from oil pollution. Oil extraction and transportation together with the effluent discharges from the coastal cities and oil refineries are among the major sources of oil pollution in the Gulf.

Kharg Island is a coral anticline in the Persian Gulf located within 28 km of the southern coasts of Iran (Figure 1). This island has a length of approximately 8 km and a width of approximately 4 to 5 km. The coastal environment of the Kharg Island is rich with corals. The corals are the host to many types of local fishes of the Persian Gulf.

Kharg Island contains the most important and biggest crude oil export terminal of Iran. More than 90% of the Iranian oil

exportation is conducted through the Kharg Island. In addition many other oil related activities including storing and filtering of the crude oil are active in the Island.

Hosting extensive oil related activities during the past 50 years has subjected the marine and coastal environment of Kharg Island to huge amount of oil discharges from different sources including oil tanker accidents, leakages at the oil terminals, discharge of oily effluents from crude oil stores and oil refineries. However, surprisingly, There are only a few studies conducted on the oil pollution around Kharg Island.

Figure 1. Kharg Island location in The Persian Gulf

DOI: 10.2112/SI65-017.1 received 07 December 2012; accepted 06 March 2013.

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In this paper, the oil pollution and its origin in the near shore coastal sediments of the Kharg Island are presented and discussed using the analysis of the concentration of hydrocarbons in the sediment samples collected early 2012 from 11 points around the Island.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Near shore sediment samples were collected at 11 points around the Island (Figure 2 and Table 1). The stations were selected in a way that they cover the whole parts of the Island's coastline. The samples were also more concentrated near the oil terminals. All of the samples were taken near the coastline at knee deep water points in low tide condition. About 200 to 300 grams of wet sediment was taken from the top 5 centimeter of surface sediment and was poured into boron silicate vial which was washed by washer material, hot water, acetone solution and distilled water and had a lid of polyethylene. The collected samples were packed and protected for transferring to laboratory using the USEPA-sw-846 standard method.

The standard method of American Association of Environmental Protection (USEPA-SW-846#3540C) named SOXHLET has been used for the preparation samples and extraction of petroleum hydrocarbons from them. The samples were passed through a 63 micron sieve (<63) before the lab analysis.

A Gas chromatography device (GC-FID) Model VARRIAN was used for determining the concentration of Total Petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) and Aliphatic and Aromatic compositions in the sediment samples. In addition, the concentration of petroleum normal alkanes with different numbers of carbons (n-c 10, n-c 35) and abundance of PAHs compositions were measured.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH)

Figure 3 shows TPH concentrations in surface sediment samples collected along the coastlines of the Kharg Island. The concentrations varied from a very low amount of 1 µg/g to very high amount of 5624 µg/g. The highest TPH concentrations which were observed at stations 2, 3 and 4, were 5624, 1660 and 4186 µg/g, respectively. These stations were located on the eastern coast of the Kharg Island near the T-shape quay, the major crude oil export terminal in the Island. The results indicate that the leakage from the loading activities have highly polluted the coastal area around the T shape quay. Stations 9 and 10, which are located near Azarpad jetty on the west side of the Island, have relatively high TPH concentration, 141 and 75 µg/g, respectively. The oil pollution in this area is resulted from the oil leakage in Azarpad oil terminal and also tanker incidents. The lowest amount of TPH concentration observed in stations 1, 7, 8 and 11. The TPH concentrations at these stations were, <1, <1, 2 and 32 µg/g, respectively. Station 1 was located in the south of the T shape quay and is somehow close to this oil terminal. However, considering the dominant direction of the wind waves on the eastern coast, the sediments in the position of this station were not affected from the oil discharges near the T shape quay. Stations 7 and 8 positioned on the northern part of the Island are far from the oil pollution sources near the oil terminals and were not affected from these sources either.

TPH concentrations at stations 5 and 6 were 78 and 232 µg/g, respectively. The concentrations in these stations are much less in comparison with the stations 2, 3 and 4 adjacent to the T shape oil

Figure 2. Location of coastal sediment sample stations in in Kharg Island

Table 1. Characteristics of sediment samples of coastal stations in Kharg Island. *H* = Water depth (cm); *p*(%) = Percentage of fine particles (<63 microns)

Stations	Latitude	Longitude	H (cm)	P (%)
1	N29 12.719	E50 19.658	70	1.50
2	N29 13.197	E50 19.793	100	36.50
3	N29 13.441	E50 19.676	75	14.40
4	N29 13.985	E50 19.677	90	37.00
5	N29 14.674	E50 19.664	65	2.90
6	N29 15.248	E50 19.969	80	6.90
7	N29 16.389	E50 17.941	70	0.20
8	N29 14.277	E50 17.834	75	0.10
9	N29 13.803	E50 18.022	75	0.20
10	N29 12.733	E50 18.500	100	1.10
11	N29 12.509	E50 19.438	100	11.10

terminal. However, the T shape quay seems to be the source for the oil content of the sediments at these stations as well.

Commendatore and Esteves, in 2007 divided coastal areas into three categories from the view point of oil hydrocarbon rate: low concentration (µg/g < 10), low to average (10-100 µg/g) and average to high (100-1000 µg/g).

Readman et al, in 2002 considered the sediments with concentration above 100 µg/g as polluted.

Tolosa et al, in 2004 considered the sediments with concentration above 500 µg/g as severe polluted and the ones with concentration less than 10 µg/g as non-polluted.

Regarding to the above criteria the sediments on the eastern part of the Kharg Island adjacent to the T shape quay can be considered as highly polluted. The polluted area extends to the north of the T shape quay along the east coast to the positions of stations 5 and 6. On the west coast of the Island the polluted area are limited to the vicinity of the Azarpad Jetty. Apart from the above mentioned areas, the shallow water sediments around the rest of the Kharg Island in most of the west coast and in the north and south of the Island can be considered as not polluted.

Figure 3. TPHs concentrations in Kharg Island Coastal Sediments ($\mu\text{g/g}$)

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH_s)

The total concentration of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (ΣPAHs) in 8 sediment samples ranged between 9.7 ng/g and 46.7 ng/g (Figure 4). The results from stations 2, 3 and 6 (Figure 2) were not accepted and eliminated from the studies. Sixteen types of PAHs compounds were found in the sediments including: Acenaphthylene, Naphthalene, Acenaphthene, Florene, Phenanthrene, Fluoranthene, Pyrene, Chrysene, Anthracene, Benzo [a] Anthracene, Benzo [b] Fluoranthene, Benzo [k] Fluoranthene, Benzo (g,b,i) Perylene, Benzo[a] Pyrene, Dibenzo [ah] Anthracene, Indeno[123-cd] and Pyrene. Based on NOAA sediment quality guidelines, the concentration of ΣPAHs compounds more than 4000 ng/g in the sediments indicates a severe pollution and toxic conditions, while the concentration less than 100 ng/g indicates a no pollution condition (Long et al., 1995). Baumard et al (1998 a) categorized sediment samples with PAH concentration of 100-1000 ng/g as low to average polluted and sediments with concentrations above 5000 ng/g as highly polluted. Notar et al (2001) introduced PAHs concentration between 250-500 ng/g as low to average pollution indexes of sediments and PAHs concentrations above 500 (ng/g) as polluted sediments. A comparison between the ΣPAHs concentrations in the studied sediments (9.7-46.7 ng/g) with the amounts in the above criteria indicates that the concentrations of PAHs in the studied sediments in the Kharg Island coastlines were very low, and the sediments can be considered non-polluted in this regard.

Figure 4. The ΣPAHs concentrations in Kharg Island Coastal Sediments (ng/g)

The origin of aliphatic hydrocarbons (AHC)

Aliphatic hydrocarbons in the coastal sediments could be resulted from human activities or biological sources such as algae, bacteria, marine animals and terrestrial vascular plants. The origins of AHCs in the coastal sediments of Kharg Island were investigated using a set of indexes. In Kharg Island crude oil discharges are considered as the main source of marine oil pollution.

The presence of a normal alkane with certain numbers of carbons in a sediment sample could be an index for the source of the hydrocarbons. For example the presence of n-C18 in a sediment sample could indicate that crude oil is the origin of observed hydrocarbons (Clarke and Finely., 1973). Normal alkanes with odd and low carbon numbers such as n-C17 could be considered as indexes for the presence of phytoplankton hydrocarbons (Tolosa et al., 2004).

The n-C16 index is computed from division of total n-alkanes concentrations to the concentration of n-C16. The amounts of index less than 15 and more than 50 indicate that fossil or biological hydrocarbons are the sources of hydrocarbones, respectively (Clarke and Finely., 1973).

The Carbon Priority index (CPI) was defined by equation (1), (Boehm and Requejo, 1986)

$$\text{CPI} = \frac{2(n\text{-C27} + n\text{-C29})}{n\text{-C26} + (2n\text{-C28}) + n\text{-C30}} \quad (1)$$

The CPI index is about 1 for crude oil hydrocarbons, while it varies from 3 to 6 for the hydrocarbons originated from vascular plants (Colombo et al., 1989).

The Odd/Even index (Volkman et al., 1992) is the ratio of the total concentrations of odd carbon number alkanes to the total concentrations of even number ones. This ratio is about 1 for crude oil hydrocarbons and varies between 8 and 10 for plant waxes.

Figure 5 presents the normal alkanes concentrations in Kharg Island coastal sediments. At stations 2, 3 and 4, with maximum TPH concentrations (Figure 3), there were high concentrations of n-C18, indicating that hydrocarbons in the sediments were mainly from crude oil. Other indexes at these stations were in agreement with n-C18 index. For example n-C17 concentrations were very low, n-C16 index magnitudes were all less than 15 and both CPI and Odd/Even indexes were about 1. This conclusion is somehow obvious because the stations were all located near the major crude oil terminal in the Kharg Island (Figure 2).

At stations 8 and 9, with moderate TPH concentrations (Figure 3) and located near Azarpad oil terminal (Figure 2), the concentration of n-C18 in comparison with other components were considerable, CPI index magnitude were between 3-6, and Odd/Even index magnitude was about 1, totally indicating that crude oil was the major source of sediment oil contamination at these stations.

Station 5 and 6 are located at the eastern coast of the Island with some distance from the T-shaped quay (Figure 2). In these stations the TPH concentrations were much lower than the ones near the T-shaped quay (Figure 3). As can be seen at Figure 5, the n-C18 and n-C17 concentrations were present at these stations. CPI index magnitudes were between 3 and 6 for both stations. The n-C16 index was <15 for station 5 and >50 for station 6. The Odd/Even index was about 1 for station 5 and 8-10 for station 6. The results indicate that hydrocarbons at station 5 have both crude oil and plant origins, while the ones at station 6, with more distance from the T-shaped quay, had plant origins.

The indexes computed for the station 7 in the northern part of the Island and stations 1, 10 and 11 in the southern part of the Island (Figure 2), all with low amounts of TPH concentrations

(Figure 3), indicated biological origins for the hydrocarbons in the sediments at these stations.

Figure 5. Normal Alkanes Concentrations in Kharg Island Coastal Sediments (continues in page 5)

Figure 5. Normal Alkanes Concentrations in Kharg Island Coastal Sediments

CONCLUSIONS

Oil pollution and origin in surface coastal sediments of Kharg Island in the Persian Gulf were studied using the analysis of the sediments at 11 stations around the Island. The levels of total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) concentrations in the sediments collected near the T-shaped quay, the major oil terminal in the Island, were very high and the sediments were categorized as chronically contaminated by oil. The TPH concentrations near Azarpad oil terminal in the west of the Island were also considerable. However, in the northern and southern parts of the Island the levels of TPH concentrations were low and these coastal areas could be considered as non-polluted by oil. Use of several indexes indicated that the alkanes in the sediments near the two major oil terminals were mainly

from fossil sources, while in the sediments from the station in the northern and southern part of the Island, the hydrocarbons were found to have biological origins. PAH concentrations were very low in all of the sediments collected around the Island.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work described in this publication was supported by the Iranian Offshore Oil Company that assisted us in the budget and facilities during the data collection.

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